

MEYER'S SYNTHESIS OF PYRIDINES FROM AMINOACRYLO- NITRILES : VERIFICATION IN THE LIGHT OF GASTALDI'S OBJECTIONS

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The reactions of dinitriles have been extensively studied by V. Meyer and have proved to be a fruitful source for the preparation of pyridines. A typical member of the series has been obtained by Gastaldi from the corresponding pyrilium salt and has been found to be different. This questions the correctness of the structure of Meyer's compounds. In the present investigation it has been shown that the structures of Meyer's compounds as a class are not incorrect, but so far as the particular member is concerned, Gastaldi's contention probably holds good and Meyer's compound may have to be represented differently.

Meyer has developed a method for the synthesis of pyridines. β -Amino- β -methylacrylonitrile was condensed with benzylidene-acetophenone in presence of sodium ethoxide to yield 3-cyano-2:4-diphenyl-6-methylpyridine (I). The cyano group was hydrolysed with concentrated HCl at 260° to the carboxy derivative (II) which, when heated with lime, lost carbon dioxide and gave 2:4-diphenyl-6-methylpyridine (III), m.p. 156°. The compound (II) on oxidation with permanganate gave 2:4-diphenylpyridine-5:6-dicarboxylic acid (IV), m.p. 185° (V. Meyer and Irmscher, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1908, II, 594).

Gastaldi has thrown considerable doubt on this reaction. He has obtained (VI) from acetophenone or dypnone by the action of acetic anhydride in presence of ferric

chloride and treating the resulting pyrilium salt (V) with ammonia and found it to be different from (III), m.p. 73°. Oxidation of (VI) with permanganate in 5% sulphuric acid gave an acid (VII), the sodium salt of which on heating with lime at 400° formed 2:4-diphenylpyridine (VIII) (cf. *Chem. Zentr.*, 1922, III, 778 ; 1923, I, 759).

The author while studying a reaction, similar to that of Meyer (this *Journal*, 1937, 14, 355), obtained products which were assigned structures based on certain experiments which definitely proved the constitution of the dicarboxypyridine compound (IV) and indicated that Meyer's mode of representing the reaction as a class is not incorrect. Those experiments form the subject matter of the present communication.

In the light of Gastaldi's research it became necessary to investigate Meyer's reaction more critically and for this purpose, in the first instance, the reaction was slightly modified in such a way that any chance of ambiguity was very much restricted. Thus, β -amino- β -phenylacrylonitrile was condensed with *O*-ethyl ether of dibenzoylmethane, a substance which can hardly be expected to react in any abnormal way. The product formed was identical with 3-cyano-*sym*-triphenylpyridine, obtained by Meyer from the same aminonitrile and benzylidene acetophenone (*loc. cit.*). This reaction can scarcely be regarded as capable of taking any other course. Moreover, this cyanopyridine derivative on hydrolysis lost carbon dioxide and gave *sym*-triphenylpyridine, identical with that previously obtained by Newman from the monoxime of benzaldiacetophenone by passing dry HCl in benzene solution (*Annalen*, 1898, 302, 240). This identity with Newman's compound, formed by an entirely different method, lends support to the correctness of Meyer's compounds.

In the second instance, (IV) has also been obtained by an equally different method. Dibenzoylmethane reacts with *m*-amidophenol to form an anil (IX) which with dry HCl in glacial acetic acid solution closes up the ring to form 2:4-diphenyl-7-oxyquinoline (X) (Bulow and Issler, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 4017). It has now been obtained more conveniently by boiling *m*-amidophenol and benzylidene-acetophenone in alcoholic solution with a trace of alkali as the condensing agent. Permanganate oxidises the oxyquinoline to give 2:4-diphenylpyridine-5:6-dicarboxylic acid, identical with Meyer's compound (IV).

These evidences therefore establish the fact that Meyer's reaction is generally correct, and if there is any doubt, it must be with the individual member (III), and to settle this issue it was thought desirable to synthesise it in such a way as would definitely prove its constitution. Ethyl β -aminocorotate, which reacts with ethyl acetylpyruvate

vigorously even at 0° (Mumm and Hüneke, *Ber.*, 1917, **50**, 1568), failed to react with dibenzoylmethane with alkaline condensing agents or when heated with zinc chloride under suction. The 1:5-diketone from styrylphenyl ketone and acetoacetic ester (Knoevenagel, *ibid.*, 1902, **35**, 397) when treated with ammonia suffers intramolecular ring-closure before it can react with the latter. Next the synthesis was attempted from dypnone and acetamide by heating them together with zinc chloride in a sealed tube at 340° for 48 hours according to the method of Pictet and Stchelin (*Compt. rend.*, 1916, **162**, 876) but the analysis of the products did not agree with the pyridine in question. The following scheme was more successful.

Using methyl cyanoacetate the course of the above reaction was followed up to the bromo-ester corresponding to (XII) by Kohler, Graustein and Merrill (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 2536). With the more common ethyl ester, it was noticed that the formation of (XI) did not proceed to completion unless the mixture was maintained just alkaline throughout the reaction by occasional additions of drops of sodium methoxide solution. Bromine in glacial acetic acid converted the open-chain nitrile into the bromopyridine derivative (XII). This was reduced with HI and the product obtained (XIII) on dry distillation with excess of barium hydroxide lost carbon dioxide and gave 2:4-diphenylpyridine, identical with Gastaldi's compound (VIII). This energetically combined with methyl iodide on a water-bath and the methiodide at 300° (Ladenburg, *Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 1410, 2059; Lange, *ibid.*, 1885, **18**, 3438; Koenigs and Hoffmann, *ibid.*, 1915, **88**, 194) formed a mixture the major component of which was diphenylpyridine, but it also contained (V, m.p. 73°) which was identified by its picrate. Meyer's compound (III, m.p. 156°) was not formed. The very small amount of material at hand and the unsatisfactory yields obtained by this process precluded any further study here and the work has been taken up again with a different line of approach which will be duly communicated.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

3-Cyano-2:4:6-triphenylpyridine (I, Ph in place of Me).— β -Amino- β -phenylacrylonitrile (2.8 g.) (Holtzworth, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1889, ii, 39, 242) and dibenzoylmethane-O-ethyl ether (5 g.) (Ruheman and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 88, 462) were dissolved in absolute alcohol and introduced into alcoholic sodium ethoxide (Na, 0.46 g.). The liquid immediately assumed a deep red tint. Within half an hour it set to a semi-solid mass. Next day it was filtered at the pump and repeatedly washed with alcohol till perfectly white, yield 2 g. It was crystallised from a large volume of alcohol, m.p. 220° (Meyer, m.p. 220°). (Found: C, 86.4; H, 5.2; N, 8.5. $C_{24}H_{16}N_2$ requires C, 86.7; H, 4.8; N, 8.4 per cent).

Hydrolysis: sym-Triphenylpyridine.—The hydrolysis was effected by heating the cyano compound with fuming HCl in a sealed tube at 260° for 4 hours. On adding water a flocculent white precipitate was obtained which did not dissolve in NaOH solution. It crystallises in needles from ethyl acetate, acetone, alcohol and is least soluble in the last, m.p. 136-37° (Found: N, 4.7. $C_{22}H_{17}N$ requires N, 4.56 per cent). A mixed melting point determination with the compound obtained by Newman's method showed no depression.

7-Hydroxy-2:4-diphenylquinoline (X).—*m*-Amidophenol (2.5 g.) and styrylphenyl ketone (5 g.) were dissolved in absolute alcohol (40 c.c.) and boiled under reflux for 7 hours with the addition of a few drops of alcoholic potash. The solution turned red and on cooling set to a crystalline mass. This was collected and crystallised from benzene, yield 2 g. Unlike the crude product it no longer tarnished in air and light, m.p. 273° (turns brown). The alcoholic mother-liquor on concentration gave a further yield of 1 g. (Found: C, 85.21; H, 5.23; N, 4.67. $C_{21}H_{15}ON$ requires C, 84.84; H, 5.05; N, 4.71 per cent). Picrate, shining orange-yellow flakes, m.p. 246-47°. (Found: N, 10.8. $C_{21}H_{15}NO.C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 10.6 per cent).

Oxidation of the Quinoline Compound: 2:4-Diphenyl-5:6-dicarboxylic Acid (IV).—The oxyquinoline derivative (3 g.) was dissolved in aqueous KOH (conc., 3 g. excess was used to prevent hydrolysis on dilution) and then diluted with warm water to 450 c.c. The solution was heated on a water-bath. 5% $KMnO_4$ (Tech., 9 g.) was very slowly added to it with stirring till the mixture became permanently pink; excess of $KMnO_4$ was decomposed with SO_2 , filtered hot and the precipitated oxide extracted with hot water. The filtrate was concentrated with occasional neutralisation with dilute H_2SO_4 to a small bulk when copious gelatinous, inorganic matter separated. This was filtered off and the filtrate with copper sulphate solution precipitated a greenish blue copper derivative which was collected, washed, suspended in water and decomposed with H_2S . The gummy precipitate was extracted with warm dilute caustic soda and acidified, when a spongy mass was produced. The whole thing was extracted with ether, dried with calcium chloride and the solvent evaporated. The residue was crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 185° (gas evolution), yield too poor. (Found: C, 71.2; H, 4.4; N, 4.7. $C_{19}H_{13}O_4N$ requires C, 71.5; H, 4.1; N, 4.4 per cent).

Condensation of Ethyl Cyanacetate with Benzylidene-acetophenone (XI).—The condensation did not proceed satisfactorily unless very pure chemicals were used in absolutely dry condition. The ketone (20 g.) and the ester (14 g.) were dissolved in carefully dehydrated methyl alcohol (30 g.) and to the warm solution sodium methoxide (5% soln.) was added dropwise till distinctly alkaline. The temperature of the reaction mixture shot up and the liquid began to boil. It was then refluxed for 2 hours with repeated additions of the condensing agent (2 drops, each time) to keep it alkaline throughout. After standing overnight the solvent was removed, the residue taken up in ether, washed with sodium carbonate, dried (CaCl_2) and finally distilled. At 10 mm. pressure a few drops of cyano-ester passed off below 100° and then the temperature began to rise till at 200° tendency to decomposition was noticed. It was a very thick, viscous, transparent mass not solidifying even on keeping in ice for several days nor could it be crystallised from any solvent, yield 28 g.

Action of HBr on above Open-chain Addition Product: Formation of Ethyl 2-Keto-4:6-diphenyltetrahydropyridine-3-carboxylate.—The above light brown mass was dissolved in warm carbon tetrachloride and saturated with dry HBr. The solution on keeping in an ice chest solidified completely. On rubbing with methyl alcohol shining white flakes were obtained, m.p. $150\text{--}55^\circ$, yield 22 g. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 160° . (Found: C, 74.3; H, 6.1; N, 4.7. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires C, 74.76; H, 5.91; N, 4.4 per cent). Hydrolysis of this ester gave the acid identical with Kohler's product (*loc. cit.*).

Action of Bromine: Formation of Ethyl 2-Bromo-4:6-diphenylpyridine-3-carboxylate (XII).—The open-chain compound (XI) was treated with bromine in hot glacial acetic acid. Copious HBr was evolved and towards the end a very slight white granular precipitate appeared which was identified to be ammonium bromide, suggesting hydrolysis of a part of the material. This was filtered off, the filtrate distilled under suction and the acid fumes removed in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH. The residual thick brownish mass was boiled with water when it became nearly semi-solid but separated from solvents as an oil. The mass was next treated with hot caustic soda solution which dissolved a considerable portion of it to form a red solution from which a quantity of the ketotetrahydropyridine ester, described above, was recovered. The residue was a hard, red, impure solid which was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol with the addition of animal charcoal and kieselghur as oblong plates, m.p. $133\text{--}35^\circ$, yield very poor. (Found: Br, 20.97. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{NBr}$ requires Br, 20.94 per cent).

Reduction of the Bromopyridine Ester.—The bromo-ester (XII, 5 g.) was mixed with red phosphorus (1 g.) and hydriodic acid (d 1.94, 12 c.c.) and heated in a sealed tube at $175\text{--}180^\circ$ for 24 hours. With the disappearance of iodine vapours a colorless liquid with large crystals were obtained. The crystals turned violet on exposure to air and were soluble in warm water. These were treated with boiling potash solution and concentrated. On cooling the potassium salt separated as a rose-red solid, freely soluble in water. Acidification precipitated the acid (XIII) in an impure condition, m.p. $200\text{--}205^\circ$. The crude reduction product was refluxed with powdered barium hydroxide and a little water for 2 hours, cooled, filtered and dried.

Removal of the Carboxyl group : Formation of 2:4-Diphenylpyridine (XIV).—

The dry material was well mixed with a little more barium hydroxide and heated gently with a small free flame in a pyrex test tube fitted with a delivery tube dipping in cold water. Decomposition started with frothing and very soon an oily distillate condensed on the cooler parts of the test tube. This solidified to a pale brown solid, yield 0.5 g. from 1 g. of the crude crystals obtained in the previous operation, m.p. 68° (pure) (Gastaldi, *loc. cit.*, m.p. 69°). (Found : N, 6.2. $C_{17}H_{13}N$ requires N, 6.0 per cent). Picric acid in alcohol produced a deep yellow picrate, m.p. 189° (Gastaldi, m.p. 187°).

*2:4-Diphenylpyridine Methiodide (XV).—*This pyridine (1 g.) and methyl iodide (1.5 g.) were refluxed on a carbon lamp. Within an hour a red paste was formed which set to a glassy red solid on cooling. This was rubbed with warm rectified spirit when a yellow solid separated, m.p. 206-208°. It was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 210°. (Found : I, 34.1. $C_{18}H_{15}NI$ requires I, 34.0 per cent).

2:4-Diphenyl-6-methylpyridine.—The methiodide (4 g.) was heated in a sealed tube at 300°-315° for 2 hours affording a black transparent soft mass which was taken up in hot water, treated with concentrated NaOH solution and distilled in steam. A slightly milky liquid passed over. Extraction of the distillate with ether, followed by removal of the solvent, gave a yellow oil having a strong odour of essential oil, but on keeping this volatile portion passed away leaving a very small amount brown solid which formed a picrate, m.p. 184-87°. This was probably diphenylpyridine.

The residue after steam-distillation was mixed with enough ether. Most of the black mass went into solution having a deep brownish green fluorescence. This was separated, filtered from the slight brown precipitate formed, solvent removed and the residue crystallised from ligroin. Impure crystals separated melting at about 60°, which energetically formed picrate. This was again mostly diphenylpyridine as the recrystallised picrate melted sharply at 169°. The mother-liquor (ligroin) was evaporated off, residue taken up in a little benzene, a few drops of petrol added and allowed to concentrate in air. Some crystals separated which were removed and washed with a little petrol. These melted at 69-72° and formed a picrate melting at 212°. The exceedingly poor yield of this compound and its admixture with diphenylpyridine, which is so close to it both in solubility in different solvents and melting point, indicated the unsuitability of this method.